

Ethical Studies on Leadership in Improving the Quality of Performance and Institutional Image

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Abstract:- The institution's image can be wrong, and the performance of subordinates can decrease in quality due to the crisis factor in leadership quality. The influence of bad leadership can cause the performance of subordinates. If this happens, logistically, it will also affect the wrong image of the institution. This study aims to analyze, describe and explain leadership characteristics; analyze and identify the factors that influence leadership quality; analyze, describe, and find effective leadership patterns in improving the quality of employee performance and the institution's image. The qualitative research instrument has a literature review, observation, and interviews. It was found that the performance of subordinates is influenced by leadership. Factors influencing the decline in leadership quality can originate from the desire to get a lot of money and wealth from his position, the desire to retain office, and the desire to take advantage of opportunities and positions to get all needs without considering the effects and ways to achieve goals. Leaders with good morals will live up to institutional values and culture and leave personal interests, greed, money, wealth, and prestige to prioritize the general welfare, *bonum commune*, and responsibility for the nobility of the institution.

Keywords:- Ethical, Leadership, Improving, Performance, Image.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many problems occurred, seizing the serious busyness of the investigators' investigations ranging from disciplinary issues, laziness, escape from responsibility [1], forgery, loss of documents or valuables [2], money laundering [3], the corruption that befell institutions [4], to shootings that resulted in death [5]. Everything does not only come from subordinates but also from a leader, such as the problem of the death of Brigadier Nofriansyah Yosua Hutabarat, who was suspected of being involved in Inspector General Ferdy Sambo in the crime of premeditated murder. Hence, until now, he is still on trial [6].

As mentioned above, problems that fall into the category of administrative crimes, criminal crimes, and even moral crimes logically touch on the quality of leadership and indicate a decrease in performance quality and tarnish the institutional image. It becomes the basis for management evaluation to improve the institutional image.

The institutional perspective is essentially characterized by shared responsibility. It becomes the basis for evaluating the performance of subordinates. The quality of employee performance can be realized not solely because of individual activities (the actor's responsibility) but also of leadership. If the employee's performance is poor, what is asked is not only what the actor (employee) does but also what is the role of the leader and how the leadership pattern is applied. This perspective is justified because previous researchers have empirically proved that leadership influences the performance of subordinates [7-9]. Leaders can influence the performance of their subordinates by motivating their employees [10]. Motivating is one of the ways a leader influences his subordinates. The positive influence of dreamers on the performance of subordinates will have a positive impact on the institutional image. Likewise, leaders' negative influence on subordinates' performance will give a bad image for institutionalization.

The main target of the concentration of institutional quality improvement is the role of leaders and subordinates. Structurally, the leader is the single organ at the top and has the task of managing the course of an organization through the performance of its subordinates. For the wheels of the organization to spin, leaders try to influence their subordinates as much as possible [11].

How should a leader and subordinates carry out their responsibilities? What needs to be done and fought for by a leader and subordinates if interests clash with the institutional culture? Is it permissible for a leader and subordinates to behave and act outside their primary duties and functions for the good of the institution? What are the factors that can affect the quality of leadership? These questions touch on assessment from an ethical perspective. Therefore, an ethical leadership assessment must be conducted to improve performance and institutional image quality.

II. LEADERSHIP, PERFORMANCE, AND IMAGE

Leadership, performance, and image are the essential attributes of an institution. Every organization must have leadership. Leadership exists to define performance. The effect of the relationship between leadership and performance is the image. The following describes these elements separately.

A. Leadership

The understanding of leadership has shifted according to the times.

- Classical leadership theories. Classical leadership theory includes trait, behaviour, and situational contingency theories. Trait theory explains that leadership is related to the characteristics of a leader. Traits associated with leadership include capacity, achievement, responsibility, participation, status, and situation [12]. Behaviour theory explains how leaders guide and motivate subordinates to be oriented towards tasks and people. Apart from being an autocratic leader by determining policies for members, giving tasks in an informative manner, setting steps that members must carry out, strictly controlling the implementation of tasks, interacting with members limited, not developing member initiatives, also prioritizing human relations, and prioritizing democratic style and participatory. With a democratic leadership style, leaders encourage members to determine their policies, provide views on steps and results obtained, provide freedom to start tasks, develop initiatives, maintain extensive communication and interaction, and implement supportive relationships between them [11]. Situational contingency theory explains that certain traits or behaviours of leadership will appear depending on the organizational environment. Organizations with specific problems will become the basis for a leader's leadership implementation.
- New leadership theory emphasizes personal characteristics such as the need for independence and capability. This perspective relates to leadership norms, such as transactional and servant leadership. Transactional leadership refers to the formal relationship of propriety between leaders and subordinates in which subordinates receive rewards or prestige to fulfil the leader's wishes [13]. Leaders motivate followers to perform beyond expectations by changing subordinates' attitudes, beliefs, and values. In this case, the leader clarifies the subordinates' needs that will be met by accepting work. Servant leadership implies that leaders must serve their subordinates [11].
- Contemporary leadership theory holds that leaders must have complex abilities to integrate and differentiate socially, cognitively, and behaviorally according to context and be able to adjust behaviour [11]. Leaders, in this perspective, must build individual relationships with subordinates [14]. Leaders must set, align direction, and motivate subordinates to achieve goals [15].

From classical leadership theory to contemporary leadership theory, the understanding of leadership is related to the efforts of leaders to influence subordinates. The influence of leaders over subordinates is only possible because of a leader's values that affect the quality of his leadership. However, understanding leadership is relatively simple because the understanding of leadership cannot be separated from two elements, namely, leaders and subordinates. It logically refers to a simple structure. Vertically, the leader occupies the top position to see, study, and find all organizational and subordinate problems to

overcome or find a way to achieve goals. Top-level leaders can correct, control and criticize subordinate performance errors. Leaders in this position are role models or good examples for achieving common goals.

Horizontally, the leader is at the forefront of directing subordinates to stay within the cultural area and institutional values. Leaders are in the front implies the courage to sacrifice and take risks for the safety of subordinates. It means that leaders are willing to sacrifice personal interests to prioritize the interests of subordinates or common interests. Leaders in this position must have the capability and skills to guide and direct subordinates to the right path. The leader is at the same time responsible for the ups and downs of the organization

B. Performance

Performance or work performance refers to the quality and quantity of the work of individual groups within an organization. Implementing these tasks is guided by norms, standard operating procedures, measurements, and criteria that have been established and applied within the organization [11]. Performance can also be understood as acquiring the results of work functions within a particular time [16]. Performance is employee work productivity, both in quality and quantity, carried out effectively and efficiently within the organization [17]. The work results, both in quality and quantity, are carried out according to the responsibilities given [18-19]. Some of these meanings provide a clear understanding for us that performance contains several elements related to it. These elements, namely: work results, productivity or performance, are measurable in quality and quantity, express ability, experience, work process, time limit, and responsibility.

Thus, it can be fully understood that performance is a result of work that expresses productivity or work performance because it is measured in terms of quality and quantity, according to the process and time that is planned and determined, characterizes experience and competence, and is carried out in a good and responsible evaluation. Good performance can be the basis for considering an effective institutional management process. The benchmark for a valued individual or group is performing. If performance is considered good, the individual or group gives a good image for themselves and the institution. A good image comes from good performance. Therefore all forms of appreciation, compensation, motivation and salary, which are workers' rights, are given based on performance or work performance considerations. The size of the right is determined by whether or not the performance is excellent or optimal and whether the performance is not.

C. Image

Everyone has an assessment and description of tangible and intangible objects. The product of thought activity can be positive or negative. Positive thoughts about a specific object form a negative image. Conversely, thinking negatively about the object produces a negative image. The image can then become a handle and guideline for generalizing the

totality of objects. A positive image will positively impact the relationship pattern and closeness to the subject or object encountered. Conversely, a negative image reduces relational qualities, becomes an obstacle, and limits positive movement.

An image is a set of beliefs, ideas, and one's impression of a specific object [20]. Image is not just an impression but a belief. Because the image is more of a belief, it has gone through the considerations, judgments, and judgments of reason. Therefore, the image becomes the basis for standing and a guide to behaviour. From this perspective, understanding will affect the cognitive structures that exist in the minds of individuals related to specific concepts [21]. The cognitive structure in question is a series of one's knowledge of a specific object or material. This knowledge is obtained by someone, both from experience in everyday life and based on concepts (including physics concepts) that have been studied and understood before [22].

An image based on empirical knowledge and knowledge of physics is intended as objective knowledge that cannot be refuted (Axios). This perspective must be realized and understood more deeply because it influences personal activities. It is pretty challenging to change his image if he has confirmed the truth of his knowledge. Image change is only possible if a rational investigation produces new and factual truths. If new knowledge and truth cannot be proven, then this cannot affect a change in the image.

III. LEADERSHIP CHARACTERISTICS

The success of an organization in achieving its goals can be due to the success of leadership. Many empirical findings have succeeded in proving the influence of leadership on performance [7]; [9]; [23-24]. Therefore, many leaders apply different leadership characteristics to achieve good performance or organizational goals. Several leadership characteristics can be observed: task-oriented leadership, relationship-oriented leadership, people-oriented leadership, money-oriented leadership, position-oriented leadership, and prestige-oriented leadership.

A. Task-Oriented Leadership

The characteristics of task-oriented leadership show that the leader considers the task to be the primary and first element in the organization. Leaders realize that a task unites every individual in the organization. Duty is the foundation and purpose of fellowship. Tasks form the basis of the individual's relationship with the organization. The rights obtained by individuals in the organization are based on consideration of the tasks carried out. No duties, no rights. This perspective is why leaders with this characteristic type always motivate and encourage task execution.

The characteristic of task-oriented leadership is a form of active leadership. It means that leaders are proactive and reactive in their role as leaders. Apart from being active, there is a non-active approach where the leader relinquishes responsibility and tries not to make decisions [25]. Task-

oriented leaders always recognize the achievements of subordinates and explain expectations; correct problems and point out errors that occur; make corrections if the problem becomes chronic, serious, and urgent.

B. Relationship-Oriented Leadership

Relationship-oriented leaders tend to build good relationships with their subordinates. To build good relationships, leaders always try to build the confidence of subordinates for the achievements that have been achieved. The leader instils a sense of pride and appreciation for his subordinates. Another way leaders develop good relationships with subordinates is by emphasizing the collective meaning of the mission, values and beliefs. It is intended so that subordinates continue to live up to the institutional values and culture and still have a good relationship with the leadership and the institution. Relationship-oriented leaders constantly seek to express a sense of enthusiasm, optimism and self-assurance. Leaders are also willing to develop, train, and teach subordinates. In addition, leaders always recognize the achievements of their subordinates and explain the expectations they want to strive for [25].

Relationship-oriented leaders consider it essential to have a good relationship between leaders and subordinates. In addition to a sense of appreciation and recognition, subordinates feel at home and comfortable carrying out their duties and responsibilities properly to attain common goals and aspirations. Bad, disharmonious relationships are the basis of the problem, which will hinder achieving maximum performance.

C. People-Oriented Leadership

The characteristics of people-oriented leadership look more at the human aspect as an essential element that needs to be valued and considered for all needs and interests. All rules and policies made are always in consideration to fulfil human needs. Thus applies the principle, "rules are for humans and not humans for the sake of rules". Rules are instruments that can be used to regulate the fulfilment of the rights and obligations of all organization members.

Leaders view employees as valuable assets that need attention. It is crucial because employees are the lifeblood of the organization's sustainability. Employees determine institutional identity. Without employees, there is no organization. Therefore leaders always protect the existence of employees, get along with them, and try to overcome all the problems they face. Leaders with this characteristic type have a heart that is always humble, altruistic and democratic.

D. Money-Oriented Leadership

Money-oriented leadership characteristics see money as everything. Leaders work, design, postpone, and decide on an action or program in consideration of getting money. Money is used as the basis for organization, basis and leadership orientation. Leaders can make money to solve all problems that individuals or groups encounter, including

obstacles that leaders encounter in carrying out leadership-related matters.

The characteristics of money-oriented leadership lead leaders to encourage their subordinates to try to earn more money from their work. Money is used for performance success. The ability and skills of subordinates to take advantage of opportunities and create opportunities to earn more and more money is the path to individual comfort and sustainability in the organization. Subordinates can be sacrificed, ignored, transferred, and even dismissed if they cannot earn money. This perspective is urgent if acquiring leadership positions is based on money.

E. Position-Oriented Leadership and Prestige

Leadership positions are the rights of all members of the organization. Even so, there are leaders who, from the start, intend to become leaders. In this perspective, the leader tries with all his strength to maintain the leadership position he is currently holding.

Position-oriented and prestige-oriented leaders tend to be arbitrary in their decisions and policies. In this perspective, abuse of power can occur. Leaders prioritize positions over humanity, human resources, and social justice. Leaders with position-oriented characteristics think that position determines self-esteem and greatness, so they take advantage of their position and do not want to lose it. He or she is unaware that the power he or she has is distributive (legal-distributive power legitimacy) and not eternal. This loss of awareness causes leaders to prioritize their interests rather than the common interest.

The effort of a leader to occupy a leadership position is a prestige. This perspective influences a leader to prioritize praise over service quality.

IV. FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE THE QUALITY OF LEADERSHIP

A. Internal Factors

Internal factors that influence leadership are factors that are found within the organization as well as the individual factors of the leader.

➤ *Individual Factors*

- Proficiency and skills significantly affect leadership. The quality of one's leadership does not exist by itself. Leaders must deepen their abilities as leaders. Leaders must continuously train their abilities and skills to understand problems and learn to take alternative steps to solve them. Therefore, involvement in formal meetings and discussions will be indispensable. Leaders need to improve their skills and abilities in decision-making. Involvement in discussional associations helps leaders to be more successful in their leadership. Leaders who have extensive knowledge will help them in making organizational decisions.

- Personality has a specific influence on leadership. An extrovert will influence leadership patterns that are more open, sociable, and friendly, speak in front of many people, and quickly adapt to a new environment. Otherwise, an introvert influences leadership that is more self-focused and introverted. In addition, the sanguine personality will affect a leader who is inconsistent in making decisions, hesitant in taking action and prefers to be alone.
- Relational. A leader who has good quality social relations is easy to get along with, and adapts easily to the environment will tend to be democratic and always open to receiving criticism and suggestions for improvement.
- Sexuality. A female leader is undoubtedly different from a male leader. Female leaders tend to be motherly, sensitive, patient, and less reactive-aggressive. Meanwhile, male leaders are bolder in making decisions and more rational.
- Prayer life. A leader who has faith and piety to God Almighty upholds human values in his leadership. The leader realizes that all of God's creations have the same value in God's eyes, so the leader always respects collective decisions and prioritizes implementing justice and the common good.

➤ *Organizational Factors*

• *Availability of funds*

The funding factor influences leadership. Available funds can trigger a creative leader in utilization and management. Conversely, limited funds will affect leaders who tend to be careful and full of calculations.

- HR (human resources) is an essential factor that also influences the pattern of leadership. HR employees who are limited in quality and quantity influence leaders to be innovative and creative in empowerment programs.
- Leadership is needed to increase employee performance. For example, an educational institution that wants to improve its quality leaders must consider the importance of supporting facilities for the learning process [26]. The facilities include libraries, teaching materials, and laboratories [27].
- Technology affects shifts in leadership patterns. Leaders can use technology tools to build practical leadership. Technology facilitates and speeds up information, monitoring of subordinates, and decision-making.

B. External Factors

- Family. Everyone works to support their family, including the leader. Therefore, family factors also influence the leader's decision. The leader's various household problems will undoubtedly influence the concentration and quality of the leader's ethical considerations. Leaders in a dilemmatic conflict need fair and proportional value judgments that do not negatively impact the organization or family.

- **Politics.** Political leaders who have the legitimacy of legal power from the public or executive departments in companies are always expected to support the community's welfare. The common good must control all formulations and policies of the leadership, so it is necessary to evaluate the potential negative impacts experienced by the community. This perspective alludes to a concern for social responsibility.
- **Economy.** A leader in economic awareness is required to take into account the benefits of institutional processes and activities. To achieve these benefits, a leader needs to take economic action by calculating small budget expenditures to calculate the maximum profit for the company's long-term sustainability.
- **Culture.** Organizational culture also influences the pattern of leadership. Many studies have tested this effect [28]; [7]. In an organizational culture, a leader is expected not to be arbitrary with his leadership. Leadership is controlled by culture, including the values contained therein. In addition to systems, mechanisms, and work procedures that bind a leader, even an innovative and supportive cultural perspective applied by a leader must be considered in the implementation of social justice or the common good.
- **Law.** The perspective of rules or laws that apply in organizations is part of a bureaucratic culture but gets particular emphasis on leadership. Although various rules and policies come from leaders as decision-makers, they apply universally to both leaders and subordinates. It means that none of the organization's members or leaders is immune to the law. Leaders must also obey a joint decision because it is a law.

V. ETHICAL PERSPECTIVES ON EFFECTIVE LEADERSHIP PATTERNS IN IMPROVING PERFORMANCE QUALITY AND INSTITUTIONAL IMAGE

Effective leadership indicators can be shown through leaders' success in dealing with employee problems and answering organizational goals. It can also be assessed through employee satisfaction with leaders in managing, supervising and deciding on everything needed and what needs to be implemented. The level of employee welfare is also an indication of a leader's success. It means that the pattern of leadership is considered adequate.

Several things need to be considered and implemented by a leader to achieve leadership effectiveness, namely:

A. *Having the spirit of God and Humanity*

A successful leader is a leader who does not rely on his abilities and strengths. A successful leader is a leader who is humble and has trust and faith in God Almighty as the source of human knowledge. A leader's leadership is effective if he is humble and asks God for strength and guidance. A leader's belief in God aims to uphold the value of justice for a civilization. Leaders will always appreciate employees and everything because it is valuable for achieving institutional goals. The leader's concern and good deeds for employees'

welfare express piety to God Almighty. Leaders with the spirit of God and humanity will treat their subordinates well. The leader will care for and watch over his subordinates as he treats himself.

B. *Having the spirit of Sacrifice*

An effective leader has a soul of Sacrifice, not for fulfilling his needs but for the happiness and welfare of all interest groups. The organization's leader is the leader of the fellowship, not the leader of himself, so he must seek satisfaction and fulfilment of personal interests. Organizational leaders are not likened to leaders in a chess game where what must be in front and sacrificed is a pawn. Organizational leaders are always at the forefront as examples and role models, including maximizing work, responsibility, service, and Sacrifice for the safety and happiness of subordinates (bonum commune). Influential leaders are not leaders who seek personal security and comfort at the expense of subordinates. An effective leader is a leader who is willing to sacrifice his time, energy, thoughts, and all his potential for the happiness and welfare of his subordinates.

C. They are maximizing the Implementation of a Supportive and Innovative Culture. Organizational culture includes bureaucratic, supportive, and innovative cultures [11]. In addition to having to work, design and make decisions related to their primary duties and functions, leaders must be open to efforts to create a climate conducive to employee support and innovation in achieving common goals. Leaders who focus on improving a supportive and innovative culture will significantly open up opportunities for performance improvement so that the institution's image is considered good. Leaders and subordinates are directed to work optimally in pursuing the implementation of the vision and mission rather than rules that can be rigid and have an impact on inefficiency and ineffectiveness. All organization members are directed to help and support each other to achieve common goals.

D. Be sensitive to the problems and needs of subordinates. Many problems pile up and go unresolved, as evidence that leaders are often insensitive to problems and needs. A leader must be sensitive and aware that subordinates are the wheels of the organization. When the wheel encounters a problem, it means that the organization is not moving or moving but limping. Therefore, leaders must be sensitive and responsive to any problems and needs of subordinates. This sensitivity will significantly assist in an efficient and effective handling process.

E. Having good morals and do not use any means to achieve goals. To maintain power, a leader does not have to justify any means [29]. Leaders must apply good deeds because everyone looks for good, not evil. The leader will gain the community's sympathy by doing a good deed, such as helping those in need. On the other hand, evil deeds will even cause resistance and curse. Leaders who have good morals will produce decisions that are

purposeful and have a positive impact on the common good (*bonum commune*). Good leaders are committed to rejecting evil as per Thomas Aquinas' imperative perspective, "*bonum est faciendum et prosequendum, et malum vitandum*" [30]. This principle means "do good, reject evil".

VI. CONCLUSION

The simple structure of an organization consists of leaders and subordinates. Leaders lead subordinates to increase performance so that it has a positive impact on the image of the institution. Leaders influence the performance of subordinates. However, many organizations do not optimally achieve their goals because of many influencing factors. Factors that affect leadership, such as decreased leadership quality, can originate from the desire to get a lot of money and wealth from his position, the desire to retain office, the desire to take advantage of opportunities and positions to get all needs without taking into account the effects and ways to achieve goals. Many internal and external factors influence leadership.

Leaders with good morals will live up to institutional values and culture and leave personal interests, greed, money, wealth, and prestige to prioritize the general welfare, social prosperity, and responsibility for the nobility of the institution. An effective leadership pattern is needed to improve the quality of performance and the institution's image. Therefore, to create an effective leadership pattern, the leader must have the spirit of divinity and humanity; be willing to sacrifice for the common good; maximize a supportive and innovative culture; be sensitive to the problems and needs of subordinates; have good moral character and do not use all means to achieve goals. Leaders must commit to rejecting evil for social prosperity (*bonum commune*).

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